

“Green chemistry and biotechnology approaches for the development of nature-based cosmetics”

GAN 101131346

Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) – Staff Exchanges

Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2022-SE-01

Project number: 101131346

Coordinator: National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA)

Project starting date: 1 March 2024

Project duration: 48 months

Deliverable D5.2

Establishment of project website and social media accounts

“Green chemistry and biotechnology approaches for the development of nature-based cosmetics”

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Consortium map

No	Name	Country
1	NATIONAL AND KAPODISTRIAN UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS	EL
2	UNIVERSITE DE REIMS CHAMPAGNE-ARDENNE	FR
3	UNIVERSITE D'ORLEANS	FR
4	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET MUENCHEN	DE
5	UNIwersytet Medyczny w Lublinie	PL
6	WYŻSZA SZKOŁA INFORMATYKI I ZARZĄDZANIA Z SIEDZIBĄ W RZESZOWIE	PL
7	FACULTE DES SCIENCES DE SFAX	TN
8	PHARMAGNOSE VIOTECHNOLOGIKI ANONYMI ETAIERIA	EL
9	ADSI-AUSTRIAN DRUG SCREENING INSTITUTE GMBH	AT
10	PHYTOWELT GREENTECHNOLOGIES GMBH	DE
11	NAT EXPLORE	FR
12	LE STUDIUM, AGENCE REGIONALE DE RECHERCHE ET D'ACCEUIL INTERNATIONAL DE CHERCHEURS ASSOCIES	FR
13	UNIVERSITE DE LA POLYNESIE FRANCAISE	PF
14	MONGOLIAN NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF MEDICAL SCIENCES	MN

A **website** for the GreenCosmIn project has been launched. It was established and is online since April 2025. The link is below:

<https://sites.google.com/view/greencosmin-dn/home>

The website serves as the main platform for communication and dissemination, offering key information, updates, and resources. It supports engagement with the general public, researchers, industry.

The website features various sections including overview of the project, consortium partners, resources (publications, conferences, etc.), and news.

Homepage of the GreenCosmIn project's website

Green

- Home
- About
- Overview
- Partners
- Resources
- News
- Contact us

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PharmaGnose
Natural Products Approaches

adsi
Assisted Drug Screening Institute

LE STUDIUM
Loise Valley
Institute for Advanced Studies

NatExplore

HELLenic REPUBLIC
National and Kapodistrian
University of Athens

UNIVERSITE DE REIMS
CHAMPAGNE-ARDENNES

Training

Development

Bioactivity

Biotechnology

Phytochemistry

phytowelt

Green CosmIn

Technical University of Munich TUM

UNIVERSITE DE LA POITOUSE FRANCIS BACON

UNIVERSITY OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY and MANAGEMENT in Rzeszów, POLAND

MEDICAL UNIVERSITY OF LUBLIN

UNIVERSITY OF SIRES TURKEY

MNUMS

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"Green chemistry and biotechnology approaches for the development of nature-based cosmetics"

Green chemistry and biotechnology approaches for the development of nature-based cosmetics

Overview

GreenCosmIn is a 4-year Horizon MSCA Staff Exchanges project that aims to form a tight multisectoral and interdisciplinary network for the implementation of

Overview page of the GreenCosmIn project's website

A screenshot of a web browser displaying the overview page of the GreenCosmIn project website. The browser's address bar shows "sites.google.com/view/greencosmin-dn/overview". The page features a dark sidebar on the left with navigation links: Home, About, Overview (highlighted in pink), Partners, Resources, News, and Contact us. The main content area has a green background with a globe and chemical structures. At the top, it says "(MSCA Staff Exchanges 2022)" and "Overview". Below this is a white box with the text "GreenCosmIn" and the logo. The main heading "Overview" is in large black font. Below the heading, the text reads "Overview of the research programme" and "GreenCosmIn will:". This is followed by a list of bullet points: "Select 20 main entities among:" with sub-bullets for plants from diverse hotspots, in vitro plant tissue cultures, and establishing clusters of bioactivity. A final bullet point, marked with a circled 'i', describes developing extracts using emerging extraction technologies.

(MSCA Staff Exchanges 2022)

Overview

Overview of the research programme

GreenCosmIn will:

- Select 20 main entities among:
 - plants from diverse hotspots (Mediterranean Basin, Central Europe, French Polynesia, Mongolia) with economic significance and established potential in terms of chemical content
 - in vitro plant tissue cultures with enhanced production of bioactive compounds
 - Establish clusters of bioactivity among the chemodiversity of the selected plants/cultures through in silico studies based on the existing natural product libraries of the participants (potential skin anti-ageing activity, tyrosinase, collagenase, elastase, hyaluronidase)
- ① • Develop extracts, enriched fractions containing the targeted bioactives, with the use of emerging extraction technologies (SFE, SWE, NADES, SPD, etc.) and DoE methodologies when needed

Publications subpage in the resources page of the GreenCosmIn project's website

Green

- Home
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 - Videos
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TUNISIA

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OF LUBLIN

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“Green chemistry and biotechnology approaches for the development of nature-based cosmetics”

Vaccinium Species—Unexplored Sources of Active Constituents for Cosmeceuticals

by Wirginia Kukula-Koch, Natalia Dycha, Paulina Lechwar, Magdalena Lasota, Estera Okon, Paweł Szczeblewski, Anna Wawruszak, Dominik Tarabasz, Jane Hubert, Piotr Wilkołek, Maria Halabalaki and Katarzyna Gawel-Beben, Biomolecules 2024, 14(9), 1110

<https://doi.org/10.3390/biom14091110>

Social media accounts for the GreenCosmIn project have been successfully established, including

❖ **LinkedIn** account (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/greencosmin>)

❖ **YouTube** channel (www.youtube.com/@GreenCosmIn)

The social media accounts serve as an effective communication tool, to raise awareness of the project, promote its objectives, broadcast its key findings and engage with multiple stakeholders and the general public.

Official LinkedIn account of the GreenCosmIn project

The screenshot shows the LinkedIn profile for GreenCosmIn. At the top, there is a banner with the text: "Green chemistry and biotechnology approaches for the development of nature-based cosmetics". Below this is the GreenCosmIn logo and a central graphic of interlocking gears labeled Training, Development, Biotechnology, Phytochemistry, and Bioactivity. To the right of the gears, it says "Horizon Europe Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions Staff exchanges (SE)".

The profile header includes the name "GreenCosmIn", the same tagline, and the text "Higher Education · 382 followers · 11-50 employees". Below this, it indicates "46 other connections follow this page" and provides buttons for "Message", "Following", and a menu icon.

The navigation bar shows "Home", "About", "Posts", "Jobs", and "People", with "Posts" selected. Below the navigation bar are filters for "All", "Images", "Videos", "Articles", and "Documents", with "All" selected. A "Sort by: Top" dropdown is also visible.

The main content area shows a post from GreenCosmIn, dated 1 week ago, with 382 followers. The post text reads: "We are pleased to share that the GreenCosmIn (CGI) consortium attended the Austrian Summit on Natural Products (Science and Technology behind Phytopharmacy..."

Official YouTube channel of the GreenCosmIn project

The screenshot shows the YouTube channel page for GreenCosmIn. At the top, there is a banner with the YouTube logo, a profile picture, and text: "Horizon Europe Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions Staff exchanges (SE)". To the right of the banner is a diagram of four interlocking gears labeled "Training", "Development", "Bioactivity", and "Phytochemistry", with "Biotechnology" written below them. Further right is the GreenCosmIn logo and a quote: "Green chemistry and biotechnology approaches for the development of nature-based cosmetics".

GreenCosmIn
 @GreenCosmIn · 16 subscribers · 11 videos
 GreenCosmIn is a 4-year Horizon MSCA Staff Exchanges project that aims to form a tight ...more
[linkedin.com/company/greencosmin/posts/?feedView=all&viewAsMember=true](https://www.linkedin.com/company/greencosmin/posts/?feedView=all&viewAsMember=true)

Buttons: Customize channel, Manage videos

Navigation: Home, Videos, Posts

Filters: Latest, Popular, Oldest

Video thumbnails and titles:

- 1:15 Introduction to GreenCosmIn partners - Phytowellt...
- 1:07 Introduction to GreenCosmIn partners-UOrleans-ICOA by Asst...
- 3:14 Introduction to GreenCosmIn partners- University of French...
- 3:38 Introduction to GreenCosmIn partners - Univ. of Reims...

The website and social media platforms are monitored to track their impact and engagement.

They serve as means to share dissemination materials, including publications, poster presentations, newspaper interviews, and updates on project activities such as consortium meetings and conference participation.

The content is updated regularly, and as of today, for example the LinkedIn profile has already attained >370 followers, >650 page views, and >750 reactions.